

CASE REPORT:

CHORIOCARCINOMA

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ABSTRACT

Choriocarcinoma is an aggressive, highly vascular tumor. When it is associated with gestation, it is often considered part of the spectrum of gestational trophoblastic disease; it is then termed as gestational choriocarcinoma. While non-gestational choriocarcinoma is not associated with prior gestation and its most common site is ovary or testis. Metastasis to liver, lung, brain and vagina may occur due to vascular invasion by tumor. Initial diagnosis of Gestational trophoblastic disease is based on a multi factorial approach consisting of clinical features, serial quantitative human chorionic gonadotropin (β -hCG) titers, and imaging findings. Ultrasonography is the modality of choice for initial diagnosis of complete hydatidiform mole and can provide an invaluable means of local surveillance after treatment. Gestational trophoblastic disease after a molar pregnancy is usually diagnosed with serial β -hCG titers; imaging plays an important role in evaluation of local extent of disease and systemic surveillance. Radio-imaging is an important diagnostic tool for diagnosis of choriocarcinoma with extent of its metastasis and management of its complications like uterine and pulmonary arteriovenous fistulas. Familiarity with the pathogenesis, classification, imaging features, and treatment of these tumors can aid in radiological diagnosis and guide to appropriate management while preserving fertility.

INTRODUCTION

Choriocarcinoma is an unusual malignant tumor having an incidence of 1 in 30,000 pregnancies. Although it may occur after any pregnancy, the most important risk

factor for choriocarcinoma is molar pregnancy. Spectrum of Gestational trophoblastic disease (GTD) include both malignant and benign gestational tumors which can be complete or partial hydatidiform mole, invasive mole, placental site trophoblastic tumor, epithelioid trophoblastic tumor and choriocarcinoma¹. The later four entities are referred to as gestational trophoblastic neoplasia (GTN). These tumors are aggressive tumors and metastasise to even distant organs. GTN can result in significant morbidity and mortality if left untreated. Early diagnosis of GTN with presence or absence of metastasis is important for successful management while preserving fertility and good prognosis. Molar gestations precede 50% to 80% of cases, and 1 in 40 molar pregnancies gives rise to choriocarcinoma. Choriocarcinoma is a purely cellular lesion characterized histological by the invasion of the myometrium by abnormal, proliferating trophoblast and the absence of formed villi. Hemorrhage and necrosis are prominent features. Early vascular invasion is common, resulting in distant metastases, most frequently affecting the lungs, followed by the liver, brain, gastrointestinal tract, and kidney. Respiratory compromise may be the initial presentation followed by venous invasion and retrograde metastasis.

Choriocarcinoma is a form of malignant GTD. It arises from cytotrophoblast as well as syncytiotrophoblast without villi, and produces human chorionic gonadotropin (Beta-hCG). By vascular metastasis it can metastasise to liver, lung, brain and vagina². Early diagnosis by various modalities of radiological investigations is crucial for deciding the modality of treatment, its prognosis and tumor response to chemotherapy³.

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CASE REPORT

A 27 year old P1L1 woman came with the complaints of bleeding per vagina since 10 months, and lower abdominal pain since 3 weeks. Patient underwent normal vaginal delivery one year ago, after which she complaint of intermittent bleeding. On USG examination a vascular RPOC was detected for which evacuation was done. Patient underwent the evacuation for 4 times for intermittent bleeding per vagina but it persisted. Her Serum Beta hCG was raised (value – 7901 mIU/ml). On 2 D transabdominal ultrasound and 3 D Transvaginal ultrasound, uterus was bulky and a large 66 x 56 mm sized heterogenous hyperechoic mass lesion was seen in endometrial cavity with few internal cystic areas, with significant increase in vascularity on colour doppler. The lesion was invading into the myometrium causing thinning of myometrium. Bilateral ovaries were visualised normally.

On MRI, a large moderately T1W hypointense, T2 W hyperintense endocavitary lesion of size 61 x 63 x 63mm was seen. Loss of endo-myometrial junction with focal site of myometrial infiltration was identified with the depth of invasion exceeding 50% of the myometrial thickness along the anterior wall. The lesion was showing mild diffusion restriction. There was no involvement of parametrium seen.

On CECT abdomen and thorax, mild contrast enhancement was seen without any evidence of pulmonary and other soft tissue metastasis. Features were in favour of neoplastic etiology of the endometrium.

Patient underwent diagnostic and therapeutic hysteroscopy suggestive of endometrial mass. Diagnosis of choriocarcinoma was confirmed on histopathology.

DISCUSSION

Choriocarcinoma is the malignant proliferation of syncytiotrophoblast, cytotrophoblast and intermediate trophoblast with absence of chorionic villi and its direct invasion into the myometrium. It is the most aggressive type of gestation trophoblastic neoplasia (GTN) with propensity to widely metastasize. It can also be non-gestational, occurring in the cervix, ovaries, and testes or outside the reproductive tract. About 50% of gestational choriocarcinoma arise from hydatiform moles; 25% are associated with term/preterm gestation, and the remaining 25% follow abortion or tubal pregnancy. Initial diagnosis of gestational trophoblastic disease is based on a combination of history, quantitative β -hCG titer, and pelvic sonography. After that a metastatic workup with CT thorax

and abdomen and MRI of pelvis is undertaken and then proved on histopathological examination⁴.

CONCLUSION

Gestational choriocarcinoma is an aggressive tumor with a propensity to widely metastasize and can result in significant morbidity and mortality if left untreated. Early diagnosis of Gestational choriocarcinoma is an essential for prompt and successful management while preserving fertility. Ultrasonography is the modality of choice for initial diagnosis, management of complications such as uterine and pulmonary arteriovenous fistulas and local surveillance after treatment.

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(A)

(B)

(C)

(D)

Fig 1 (A): Large heterogenous hyperechoic mass in endometrial cavity with few internal cystic areas. (B): colour doppler images showing significant increase in vascularity. (C): Bilateral ovaries seen separately. (D): 3D USG of the mass lesion showing bulky uterus with myometrial involvement.

(A)

(B)

(C)

(D)

(E)

(F)

Fig 2. On cross sectional imaging a T1WI large hypointense (A), T2WI heterogenous hyperechoic endocavitary mass on axial (C) and sagittal (D) with myometrial invasion, without any significant suppression on STIR (D), showing mild diffusion restriction (E,F).